

Synthesis of 1-Arylpiperazine Amides of 2-[4-(Methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dione-1-yl]acetic, -propionic Acids

K. D. THAKUR and S. D. SAMANT*

Organic Chemistry Research Laboratory, University Department of Chemical Technology, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 15 September 1992, revised 4 January 1993, accepted 7 January 1993

During last two decades *N*-(ω -aminoalkyl)imide (1) has emerged as a promising pharmacophore. Over last few years we have synthesised a series of *N*-[3-(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)alkyl]imides (2)¹. These imides show CNS depressant and cardiovascular activities.

Parallel to the preparation of these glutarimides we attempted the preparation of the corresponding glutaconimides, the unsaturated analogs of the glutarimides. Preparation of these compounds was found to be difficult. Modification of the central alkylene bridge in 1 changes the activity of the pharmacophore to a great extent. 1-Piperazine amides are reported to show diverse biological activities². The compounds to which we were attracted were 1-aryl-(4-phthaloylglycyl)/*dl*- α -alanyl)piperazines which possess antiparkinsonic activity³. Hence, we attempted the synthesis of 1-arylpiperazine amides (14, 15) of ω -[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]acetic, -propionic acids (7, 8).

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)pentendioic acid (3) was prepared by the known method⁴. Compound 3 was treated with Ac₂O to obtain the corresponding anhydride (4). Compound 4 when fused with glycine (5) gave 7. The acid chloride (9) of 7, could not be prepared by treating it with SOCl₂ or PCl₅. In every case, a mixture of irresolvable products with some tarry mass was obtained. The direct condensation of 7 with 1-arylpiperazines was also not possible; at a low temperature the reaction did not proceed and at higher temperature excessive decomposition took place. Compound 7 was esterified to 10 using EtOH. The condensation of 10 with 1-arylpiperazine also failed. On this background, we had to attempt a new route to the synthesis 14 and 15.

Compound 4 as well as *N*-substituted glutaconimides exhibit keto-enol tautomerism. Thus, 7 can

exist in tautomeric forms 7a and 7b. The enolic OH can cyclise with the COOH group. When 7 was refluxed with Ac₂O, azalactone (11) was formed. It was neutral and insoluble in NaHCO₃. It slowly dissolved in aqueous NaOH. On heating with aqueous NaOH it dissolved and the solution on acidification regenerated the parent acid (7). Ir spectrum of 11 showed lactone CO at a very high wavenumber (1855 cm⁻¹). The pyridone CO appeared at 1700 cm⁻¹. The high value of the lactone CO suggested the presence of high strain in the lactone ring; it also suggested that the ring can be opened by a nucleophile.

When 11 was heated with a series of 1-arylpiperazines in boiling acetone the lactone ring opened up to give a series of 4-aryl-1-piperazinylamides of 2-[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dione-1-yl]ethanoic acid (14).

Encouraged by this observation, we planned to prepare the next higher homolog (15) of 14. When 4 was heated with 3-aminopropanoic acid (6), 8 was obtained. When 8 was heated with Ac₂O it cyclised to azalactone (12). In the ir spectrum of 12, the lactone CO appeared at 1800 cm⁻¹ at considerably low wavenumber than that in 11, indicating less strain in the molecule. The pyridone CO appeared at 1670 cm⁻¹. When 12 was refluxed with 1-arylpiperazines (13) in boiling acetone a series of 4-aryl-1-piperazine amides of 3-[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]propanoic acid (15) were obtained.

Experimental

The m.p.s. were taken in open capillaries on a Campbell melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on Varian T-60 (60 MHz), Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) and Varian XL-100 spectrometers using TMS as internal standard.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)pentendioic acid (3) was prepared from citric acid, anisole and concentrated H₂SO₄⁴. Compound 3 on treatment with Ac₂O gave the corresponding anhydride (4). 1-Arylpiperazines were prepared from anilines and diethanolamine following the reported procedure⁵.

2-[4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1*H*,5*H*-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]ethanoic acid (7): A mixture of 4 (4.8 g, 20 mmol) and glycine (1.8 g, 24 mmol) was heated at

